

D8.2

DATA CELLAR Training plan and first materials

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Executive Summary

The aim of Deliverable 8.2, " DATA CELLAR Training and first material" is to document the training plan developed within Task 8.2 for the engagement and training of data providers and users of DATA CELLAR. This educational program aims to promote the training of industrialists, research entities and stakeholders of energy communities on how to implement the solutions and concepts developed within DATA CELLAR. The training plan will follow the "Train the Trainer" approach, therefore learning material will also be provided to trainees during the workshops and webinars that will be organized. The methodology followed for developing the training plan for DATA CELLAR is divided into two main steps: the training needs assessment and the definition of the training plan.

The training needs assessment aims to account for any training needs that the Validation Cases of DATA CELLAR might have and to identify the target groups for the training. This is an important step in order to define the different modules that need to be included in the training plan of the project. The next step of the methodology is the definition of the training plan. This includes the reporting of the goals, requirements, objectives and wanted training outcomes of the modules identified in the previous step. Moreover, this deliverable reports on the training tools that will be used during the training as well as the evaluation methods. The evaluation of the training is an important aspect that DATA CELLAR will leverage during the lifetime of the project to improve the delivery of the training and the material that will be created. Lastly, some first material is provided for some of the modules.

The training plan of DATA CELLAR has a fundamental role to play in the dissemination of the project and the DATA CELLAR data space. Having an effective training plan will allow the users to extract the maximum capabilities that the DATA CELLAR platform can offer. This report will act as a guide for the training activities of DATA CELLAR to enable the provision of quality training that will satisfy the goals and objectives of the project.

1. Introduction

Project Summary

A greener energy system is crucial for the future prosperity and liveability of European citizens. This requirement is at the heart of the DATA CELLAR approach where Local Energy Communities (LECs) have been recognised by the European Commission as a pivotal measure to play a key role in driving the EU's energy transition. At the same time, the digitisation of the EU energy system and the proper exchange of data between energy actors appear crucial to foster the exchange of best practices and the creation of a knowledge community to tackle one of our society's most pressing global crises: climate change.

Figure 1: DATA CELLAR Rationale

In this context, DATA CELLAR aims to implement a collaborative platform that will provide an interoperable and secure energy data space capable of delivering access to datasets and AI models to serve and support the spread of Energy Communities (ECs) in the European Union, leveraging on experience gained in the development of other EU projects.

DATA CELLAR will create a decentralized data space to store streams or historical data coming from private metering, but it will also provide a data federation integrating data coming from both external companies and EU federation spaces. The data space will be populated by a series of services dedicated to energy utilities, ECs, private businesses and citizens. Furthermore, DATA CELLAR will provide a decentralized and open marketplace for energy datasets and pre-trained AI models to serve and support LECs.

To achieve its objectives, DATA CELLAR is divided into 9 WPs with different objectives, tasks and deliverables. WP8 is responsible for the dissemination, communication and standardization strategies of DATA CELLAR. More specifically, during the lifetime of the project, WP8 will implement these strategies focusing on 5 different aspects. Firstly, communication and dissemination activities will be deployed with the aim to showcase the results of the project and its impact on key audiences. Secondly, an educational program will be developed with the aim to train data providers and users

on key aspects of DATA CELLAR. Thirdly, collaboration and dissemination activities will be deployed with other Horizon Europe initiatives and with DATA CELLAR's cluster of projects. Moreover, a comprehensive strategy for the project stakeholders' engagement, dissemination and communication will be designed and implemented during the interaction and exploitation of synergies with relevant EU initiatives. Finally, a policy position paper will be published related to data space and data standards for Europe.

Deliverable objectives and overview

The objective of Deliverable 8.2, "DATA CELLAR Training and first material" is to document the training plan developed within task 8.2 for the engagement and training of data providers and users of DATA CELLAR and act as a guide for training activities that will be organized. This educational program aims to promote the training of industrialists and research entities on how to implement the solutions and concepts developed within DATA CELLAR. Moreover, the training plan will follow the "Train the Trainer" approach, therefore learning material will also be provided to trainees during the workshops and webinars that will be organized.

Relation to other tasks and deliverables

Deliverable 8.2, "DATA CELLAR Training and first material" aims to facilitate the realization of an important objective of WP8 regarding the training of data providers and users of DATA CELLAR. Moreover, during the development process of the training plan, inputs were needed from various tasks and work packages (WP), especially from those who were the solutions and concepts of DATA CELLAR are being developed. The interactions with the different WP are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Relation to other tasks

Deliverable structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 1: Introduction
- Section 2: The methodology followed for developing the training plan is described.
- Section 3: the results of the training needs assessment performed before the development of the training plan are reported.
- Section 4: The training plan for DATA CELLAR is documented reporting the scope of the training, the target groups of the training, its objectives and specific targets. Moreover, the training content is described and the evaluation methods that will be used are mentioned.
- Section 5: The first material that is being developed for the training is provided.

- Section 6: Privacy guidelines that will be followed during the workshops and webinars are reported.
- Section 7: Conclusions and takeaways learned during the development progress of the training plan are reported.

2. Methodology for the development of the Training Plan

The methodology followed for developing the training plan for DATA CELLAR is illustrated in Figure 3. The methodology is divided into two main steps: the training needs assessment and the definition of the training plan. The training needs assessment aims to account for any training needs that the Validation Cases (VCs) of DATA CELLAR might have and also to identify the target groups for the training. This is an important step in order to define the different modules that need to be included in the training plan of the project. The next step of the methodology is the definition of the training plan. This includes the reporting of the goals, requirements, objectives and wanted training outcomes of the modules identified in the training needs assessment and in the Grant Agreement of the project. Moreover, where it was possible a basic structure of the module was also provided. After the first draft of the training plan was ready, the feedback of the VCs and technical partners was required to finalize it.

Figure 3: Methodology for the development of the Training Plan of DATA CELLAR.

3. Training needs assessment

The assessment of the training needs of the project was focused on two different aspects: the training needs of the VCs and the training needs that derive from the solutions and concepts developed within DATA CELLAR.

3.1. Assessment of the training needs of the Validation Cases

An important part of the training plan development procedure was to assess the needs of the VCs in terms of training. To achieve that, a workshop was organized with all representatives of the VCs. The results of the workshop are summarized in Table 1 and

Table 2.

Table 1: Results of the workshop regarding the training needs of the VCs.

Do you have any specific training needs related to DATA CELLAR?	
VC	Specific Training Needs
FAEN	Training and assistance related to the DATA CELLAR project components and direct benefits for its users.
EDG WEST	-Strategies for effectively communicating with stakeholders and highlighting the benefits of DATA CELLAR to them. -Training on the use of the AI/ML libraries and data-driven services developed within DATA CELLAR.
EMAC	EC conceptualization and role of stakeholders (including citizens)
EUNICE	-Information provided to the EC members about the developed data services and how they can benefit from them. -EC members familiarization with the Data Space utilization and training on the use of the data-driven services developed within DATA CELLAR.
IREN	-The new concepts introduced by EC (e.g., virtual consumption, incentive sharing, the meaning of “prosumer, consumer, producer); -Contractual complexity and the use of personal data in the framework of EC; -DATA CELLAR developed data services and how they can benefit from them; -Familiarization with Data Space utilization and training on the use of the data-driven services developed within DATA CELLAR.
CFOAT	-Information provided to the EC members about the data-services and how they can benefit from them (e.g., use of information from other ECs) -The use of personal data in the Data Cellar Specifics about DATA CELLAR developed tools (e.g. DSS, Digital Twin) and how they can benefit an EC
AEM	-Prospective data providers and consumers should be informed about the purposes and the possible benefits of using DATA CELLAR, as well as be allowed to receive a full description of the platform and tools that will be available if they join. -For data providers, the datasets in which DATA CELLAR is interested should be clearly defined, in addition to providing courses and guidelines on how to both connect to the platform and upload data. -For data consumers, the list of datasets with their details should be available on DATA CELLAR’s website, so that the categories of data can be consulted before connecting to the platform.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -In addition to the possible documents and guidelines that could be shared or downloaded from the DATA CELLAR website, the possibility of accessing some videos directly on the site as pre-recorded material available at any time would be attractive. -Provision of guidelines and training to enable data providers and consumers to use the tools available on the platform (e.g., Digital Twin, DSS with VERIFY, and INTEMA). -Provision of information about the data anonymization tool and the data security policy adopted by DATA CELLAR.
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Table 2: Results of the workshop regarding potential training targets.

<i>Please mention potential target groups for the training.</i>	
VC	Suggested target groups
FAEN	-Small group of technicians for the future dissemination of DATA CELLAR.
EDG WEST	-System administrator and technical team. -Other energy providers.
EMAC	- Stakeholders of the energy sector, town hall staff (utilities and energy, licencing) and citizens.
EUNICE	-Administrator and members of the EC -Local Prefectures -Organizations active in the energy production and services sector -Other ECs in Greece
IREN	-If EC members will be trained by DATA CELLAR: Administrator and members of the EC; -If EC members won't be trained by DATA CELLAR: ESCo's sales and technical teams.
CFOAT	-Directors and shareholders of the EC -ECs in the Galway and Mayo area -Local universities and regional authority for the Gaeltacht (Irish-speaking area)
AEM	-Distribution System Operators -ECs

3.2. Conclusions of the workshop

As expected, the VCs' needs are mostly focused on the different components of DATA CELLAR. A specific need is identified for the benefits that a user of DATA CELLAR can have from the different components. This was considered in the basic structure that is proposed for the tools that are still under development. In addition, other needs are also identified for training related to ECs. More specifically, the introduction to new concepts that are now used or have the potential to be used in ECs, the use of personal data in the concept of ECs, EC conceptualization and the role of the different stakeholders. To address this, a specific introductory module was created and integrated into the training plan related to ECs.

4. Training Plan Definition

In this section, the training plan developed for DATA CELLAR is reported.

4.1. The scope of this training

The development of an effective training plan is very important for the dissemination of DATA CELLAR and the increase of its impact. The scope of this training is not to only train the users and data providers of DATA CELLAR but also to follow a “Train the Trainer” approach by training stakeholders that can potentially train others.

4.2. Target groups

The target groups for the training were determined based on the Grant Agreement of the project and the results of the workshop that was organized with the VCs which was mentioned in section 3. Also, the stakeholders identified in D1.1 were also considered. The identified target groups for the training are given in

Table 3.

Table 3: Target groups for the training.

Target Group	Identified from: Workshop-WS, Grant Agreement - GA
Local authorities (Town hall staff)	GA, WS
Regional authorities (Municipalities, Regional agencies, Local prefectures)	GA, WS
National authorities (Ministries)	GA
Local associations	GA
Energy Companies	GA, WS
Technicians	WS
System administration and technical team	WS
Stakeholders of the energy sector (Energy Providers, Organizations active in the energy production and services sector, DSOs)	GA, WS
Other Energy Communities and their shareholders (Citizens, Administrator of EC)	WS
ESCO’s sales and technical teams	WS
Local universities	WS

4.3. Objectives of the training

This training plan, following the “Train the Trainer” approach, aims to provide the needed skills and capabilities to the specific target groups for the trainees to be able to pass these skills and capabilities to others. Specific objectives are given for each module in the following section.

4.4. Training Content

The identified modules for the training were divided into 5 main categories as shown in

Figure 4. A general category was defined to include modules that can be considered supportive material to the other categories. In addition, three more categories that are directly related to the main components of DATA CELLAR were defined: Digital Twin & DSS, AI Services and Marketplace. Finally, a specialized category was created with material that is targeted to a specific audience with

solid technical background. In the following sections the specific modules for each category are described.

Figure 4: Categorization of the modules included in DATA CELLAR’s training plan

4.4.1. General

Title	Introduction to DATA CELLAR	Related WP	WP1, WP2 and WP8
Category	General		
Objective	Introduce DATA CELLAR to the wider audience with emphasis on scope, objectives and impacts		
Goals and learning outcomes	Get to know the importance of Data in managing efficiently the energy-related issues in our daily life and how DATA CELLAR intends to maximise the benefits for all users. The trainees should be able to understand the concept of DATA CELLAR and its goals and to explain it to others.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	None		

Title	Introduction to Energy Communities	Related WP	WP1
Category	General		
Objective	Introduce ECs as an active contributor to the Energy Transition process. Give the basic organizational structure of ECs and a flavour of what can be collectively achieved.		
Goals and learning outcomes	To understand the organizational issues of ECs and how citizens can benefit from their own active participation.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	None		

Title	How to navigate DATA CELLAR?	Related WP	WP5
Category	General		
Objective	The objective of this module is to introduce the trainees to the DATA CELLAR’s dashboard and to show them how to use and navigate into the dataspace.		
Goals and learning outcomes	The trainees will be able to navigate into DATA CELLAR ‘s dashboard		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	Introduction to DATA CELLAR		

Title	LEC Assessment Tool	Related WP	WP1, WP7
Category	General		
Objective	The objective of this tool is to assess potential users of DATA CELLAR (ECs), to verify the actual and potential performance in terms of energy management and members’ costs, by running some simulations with a sample of the EC’s datasets, making sure that no private information is involved. The results of this simulation can provide information on the actual stage of the EC development. Furthermore, a list of DATA CELLAR functionalities will be presented as a final report. This tool is planned to be part of the data space webpage, with a proper interface for data uploading and assessment marking.		
Goals and learning outcomes	The goal of this training is to provide the users with the correct knowledge on which data must be uploaded to the “calculator” (such as energy consumption, energy tariff, EC’s members and assets information etc.), and how to read the report. The interface is planned to be as simple as possible.		

Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	Introduction to DATA CELLAR How to navigate DATA CELLAR?
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Title	The use of personal data within DATA CELLAR.	Related WP	WP2, WP5
Category	General		
Objective	The objective of this module is to briefly explain to the trainees how personal data is handled within DATA CELLAR.		
Goals and learning outcomes	The trainees should be able to understand and explain to others how personal data is handled within DATA CELLAR.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	Introduction to DATA CELLAR		

Title	Reference Design of a Smart Meter and NILM on Edge	Related WP	WP2
Category	General		
Objective	Guide participants in building a functional smart meter from scratch, using the T2.2 guide, and teach them how to install the code for NILM on Edge.		
Goals and learning outcomes	Participants will have the ability to independently build a smart meter, install it in a real-world setting, and effectively utilize the NILM on Edge model for real-time load disaggregation and energy consumption analysis on the smart meter.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	Introduction to DATA CELLAR		

Title	Principles and key aspects for the fulfilment of due diligence and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)	Related WP	WP8
Category	General		
Objective	Participants will gain knowledge to integrate responsible practices, ensuring both industry compliance and meaningful contributions to global sustainability.		
Goals and learning outcomes	<p>Upon completion, the participants should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate SDGs into marketing plans that effectively contribute to global sustainability, while considering economic, environmental, and social factors. • Identify and develop effective strategies to mitigate negative impacts against sustainable development. • Learn the importance of laying out an effective collaboration system across all the stakeholders in the value chain to drive initiatives forward. 		

Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	None
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4.4.2. AI Services

Title	Introduction to AI	Related WP	WP5
Category	AI Services		
Objective	This module will introduce the trainees to the basic aspects of AI and specific applications for the energy sector.		
Goals and learning outcomes	The trainees will be able to understand the basic principles of AI and what are the benefits of using AI in the energy sector. Moreover, an introduction to the different AI Services that DATA CELLAR offers will be performed.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	Introduction to DATA CELLAR		

Title	Training a ML model using the DATA CELLAR Visual Tool	Related WP	WP6
Category	AI Services		
Objective	Equip participants with the necessary knowledge and practical skills to effectively train a Machine Learning (ML) model using the DATA CELLAR Visual Tool.		
Goals and learning outcomes	Utilize the DATA CELLAR Visual Tool effectively to pre-process data, select features, and train ML models, as well as create the inference pipeline for model deployment on the DATA CELLAR Platform.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	Introduction to AI How to navigate DATA CELLAR?		

4.4.3. Marketplace

Title	How to use DATA CELLAR Marketplace	Related WP	WP6
Category	Marketplace		
Objective	Introduce the trainees to DATA CELLAR Marketplace.		
Goals and learning outcomes	The trainees should be able to use and navigate the Marketplace of DATA CELLAR and be able to demonstrate to others how to use it.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	How to navigate DATA CELLAR?		

Title	Loyalty platform	Related WP	WP6
Category	Marketplace		
Objective	Introduce the trainees to the loyalty platform and its different functionalities.		
Goals and learning outcomes	The trainees should be able to understand how they can benefit from the loyalty platform. Moreover, the trainees should be able to use the platform.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	How to use DATA CELLAR Marketplace		

4.4.4. Digital Twin & DSS

Title	Decision Support System (DSS) tool	Related WP	WP5
Category	Digital Twin & DSS		
Objective	Introduce and showcase the 5 different functionalities of the DSS tool. The functionalities are Optimal RES Sizing, Flexibility Estimation, DSO Resources Optimal Location, DSO Management of DSO Resources and Life Cycle Cost/Life Cycle Assessment.		
Goals and learning outcomes	The trainees should be able to use the DSS tool and be aware of the data requirements to deploy each functionality.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	How to navigate DATA CELLAR?		

Title	Data-Driven-Digital-Twin Modelling of ECs	Related WP	WP5
Category	Digital Twin & DSS		
Objective	Introduce the trainees to the digital twin tool which entails the generation of a model that replicates the original grid topology from measurements. Within this context, the application of the digital twin tool for the two DSS functionalities (i.e., F3: DSO Resources Optimal Location, F4: DSO Management of DSO Resources) will be discussed.		
Goals and learning outcomes	The trainees should gain a comprehensive understanding of the diverse applications of the digital twin tool, along with its added value.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	AI services and libraries Decision Support System tool		

4.4.5. Specialized material

Title	Architecture - Data Space operation/demonstration	Related WP	WP4
Category	Specialized Material		
Objective	Demonstration of “Exchange of data among data space participants”		
Goals and learning outcomes	Understanding of Data Space concepts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data Space type: B2B2C - Difference between data space participant/end-user - Role of federation services (identity provider & catalogue) & connector - GAIA-X compliance and self-descriptions 		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	Introduction to DATA CELLAR		

Title	DLT for Energy Data Marketplace	Related WP	WP6
Category	Marketplace		
Objective	Provide participants with a comprehensive understanding of DLT-based marketplace platforms, and familiarize with the key concept of data sharing, digital assets, remuneration and incentivisation mechanisms.		
Goals and learning outcomes	Exploring different types of marketplaces for data and AI models, such as public marketplaces, private marketplaces, and industry-specific marketplaces. Learning how to build your own data marketplace starting from existing solutions.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	Introduction to DATA CELLAR		

4.5. Training tools to be used during the webinars and in-person workshops

To maintain the “Train the Trainer” approach, any e-learning tools that will be used during the training will be publicly available or a free alternative will be suggested. This way the trainees can use them in future training sessions that they will potentially host. The training tools that will be used during the workshops and webinars are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Training tools that will be used during training

Training Tools	Preferred Tool	Free Alternative	Purpose
Online Platform	GoToWebinar	Google Meet	The online platform will be used to host the webinars that will be organized.
Slides	PowerPoint	Google slides	Most of the material that will be created will be in slides to facilitate the presentations during the workshops and webinars.
e-learning tools	Slido	Mentimeter	E-learning tools will be used during training to make the delivery of the training more interactive.
Assessment tools	Google Forms	-	Google forms will be used to enable the assessment of the modules.

4.6. Evaluation Methods

The evaluation of the training delivery and the material that will be provided is an important tool that DATA CELLAR will leverage to ensure the quality of its training activities. The evaluation methods that will be used during DATA CELLAR’s training will focus on two main aspects:

- Assessment of the Learning outcomes

For each of the modules that will be developed a short quiz will be given at the end to evaluate the learning outcomes of each module. The results of the quiz will help to tailor and improve the delivery of the training by focusing on aspects that are identified as weaknesses.

- Quality Assurance and Continuous Improvement

At the end of each webinar/workshop, a questionnaire will be circulated to the participants to evaluate their experience during the training. Regular feedback from the trainees will ensure the quality of the training.

4.7. Privacy Guidelines

To safeguard the participants’ sensitive personal information and to increase their trust in the training process, it is crucial to establish guidelines to follow existing privacy policies. These guidelines will ensure that the trainees’ data is properly handled by relevant data protection laws as mainly indicated in D9.2. As reported in Deliverable 9.2 “Data Management Plan, Ethics Self-Assessment and DATA CELLAR Ethical Protocol” the DATA CELLAR consortium comprises partners from 16 different countries and on 14 of them the GDPR is adopted since they are part of the European Union. For the United Kingdom and Norway, GDPR was also implemented through the UK Data Protection Act 2018 and Personal Data Act 2018 respectively. The specific guidelines for the training will be

consistent with Task 7.4: “Guidelines on improving data handling and sharing” and will be shared with the consortium before the commencement of training activities.

5. First training material

An important objective of Task 8.2 is the creation of material related to the training modules identified in the previous section. This material will not only be used during the training activities of DATA CELLAR but will also enable the “Train the Trainer” training requirement of DATA CELLAR by providing trainees with material that they can use to train others. Moreover, this material will be provided to academic organizations and online platforms to potentially integrate the DATA CELLAR training programme into their educational programmes. At the stage of issuing this training plan for most of the identified modules, it is not possible to create material that facilitates the targeted training outcomes, since most of the components of DATA CELLAR are still under development. In this section, the material created for two of the modules along with an extensive structure for the module, are reported. The two structures of the modules “Introduction to DATA CELLAR” and “Introduction to Energy Communities” are given in Table 5 and Table 6 respectively. Moreover, the material created for these two modules is provided in Annex A and Annex B.

Table 5: Extensive structure of the module “Introduction to DATA CELLAR”

Title	Introduction to DATA CELLAR	Related WP	WP1, WP2 and WP8
Category	General		
Objective	Introduce DATA CELLAR to the wider audience with emphasis on scope, objectives and impacts.		
Goals and learning outcomes	Get to know the importance of Data in managing efficiently the energy related issues in our daily life and how DATA Cellar intends to maximise the benefits for all users.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	None since the specific training material is introductory, and it already exists in the contract as signed.		
Structure of the content			
Introducing the project DATA CELLAR			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project overview and scope • Challenges • Project ambition • Why digital and green • Vision for technical and semantical interoperability • Main impacts of the project 			

Table 6: Extensive structure for the module “ Introduction to Energy Communities”.

Title	Introduction to Energy Communities	Related WP	WP1, WP2 and WP8
Category	General		
Objective	Introduce ECS as an active contributor to the Energy Transition process. Give the basic organizational structure of ECs and a flavour of what can be collectively achieved.		
Goals and learning outcomes	To understand the organizational issues of ECs and how citizens can benefit from their active participation.		
Prerequisites modules of DATA CELLAR	None, since the specific training material is introductory, and it already exists in the contract as signed.		
Structure of the content			
Introduction to Energy Community - Training – Presentation Outline			
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Definition and Purpose of Energy Community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the concept of an EC • Explaining the goals and objectives of forming an EC 2. Benefits and Importance of Energy Community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifying the advantages of collaborating within an EC • Highlighting the positive impact on sustainability, affordability and resilience 3. Energy Sources and enabling technologies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable Energy • Defining Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and their characteristics • Exploring solar, wind, hydroelectric, geothermal and biomass energy 4. Enabling technologies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage and use of flexibility in managing local resources • Smart, digitalised and interoperable integrated grid • Managing data to serve the integrated grid 5. Energy Conservation and Efficiency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognizing the importance of energy conservation and its role in sustainability • Tips and strategies for improving energy efficiency in everyday life 6. Quiz: Test Your Knowledge <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short quiz to assess learners' understanding of the concepts covered 7. Recap and Key Takeaways <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Summarizing the key points • Reinforcing the significance of energy community and sustainable energy practice 			

At the time of elaborating this training plan, the tools and services of DATA CELLAR are still in the development stage. To ensure that the material for the modules related to the tools of DATA CELLAR

satisfies the requirements of the training, a basic structure was formed to be used when material for the tools and services will be created.

Table 7: Basic Structure for the modules related to the Tools and Services

Basic Structure for the modules related to the Tools and Services	
A/A	Section
1	Introduction to the Tool <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential Benefits to the User • Where the tool can be implemented and for what reason
2	Inputs required for the tool <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific datasets that are required for the operation of the tool. • Indications on where to find the needed datasets
3	Expected outputs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results from using the service
4	Demonstration of the Tool <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of the tool for at least one case study • Potential application of the tool by the trainee
5	Outline and Conclusions

6. Conclusions

The training plan of DATA CELLAR has a fundamental role to play in the dissemination of the DATA CELLAR project and data space. Having an effective training plan will allow the users to extract the maximum capabilities that the DATA CELLAR platform can offer. As the components and concepts of DATA CELLAR mature and the training activities begin, the training content must be continuously updated and adjusted. To facilitate that, an assessment strategy for the material will be deployed during the lifetime of the project to account for any extra needs and feedback from the trainees.

At the time of defining the training plan, it was determined that it was not realistic to define the scheduling of the training since most of the components and were not ready. However, specific goals were set in line with the KPIs of the project, a provisional deadline was established and the next steps were decided. During the lifetime of the project, at least 6 in-person workshops and 10 webinars will be organized. To achieve these goals the in-person workshops will co-exist with the next General Assemblies of the project. Moreover, a training calendar will be formed to schedule the rest of the in-person workshops and webinars. The material that will be created will be ready by M27 when the first training of the VCs will take place.

7. Annex A

This annex includes material created for the module “Introduction to DATA CELLAR”.

Consortium members: 31 partners, one mission

 Scientific knowledge in the framework of energy systems		
 Training		
 Validation Cases		

3

Data Cellar – Challenges

 LACK OF STANDARDS ↓ INTEROPERABILITY ↓ STANDARDIZATION AND CERTIFICATION OF BUILDING BLOCKS			
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4

Energy Communities as pivotal in EU Energy Transition

1 DEMOCRATIZATION

- ✓ CITIZENS/ USER ENGAGEMENT
- ...

2 DIGITALISATION

- ✓ DIGITAL TWIN
- ✓ DSS TOOL
- ✓ AI MODELS
- ...

3 DECENTRALIZATION

- ✓ FEDERATED DATA SPACE

4 DECARBONISATION

- ✓ RENEWABLE GENERATION
- ✓ OPTIMAL MANAGEMENT
- ✓ SECTOR COUPLING
- ...

EPL TECHNOLOGY FRONTIERS | DATA CELLAR

Data Cellar – Project Overview and Scope

DATA CELLAR will develop a dynamic, interoperable energy-oriented data platform to support the creation and operation of Energy Communities

MAIN OBJECTIVES

- Deliver **data-driven energy services** to support the energy transition
- **Development, validation and demonstration** of a **dynamic data hub**
- **DLT-based open marketplace** and **novel business models**
- Implement **privacy and cybersecurity-by-design**

EPL TECHNOLOGY FRONTIERS | DATA CELLAR

Ambition

- Create a public energy data space that will support the creation, development and management of Local Energy Communities (LEC)
- Based on an open and interoperable cloud-to-Edge data Exchange architecture & aligned with current and future EU data spaces initiatives
- DLT-Driven Marketplace to engage users and extract value of data and pre-trained AI models

Data cellar why: Green

EU has set itself a target to collectively reach a share of at least 42.5% renewables in final energy consumption by 2030, with more than 60% of the electricity coming from RES, while the electricity should be 100% carbon free by 2050.

1

Energy Communities play a fundamental role in a sustainable transition and decarbonization of our future, enabling new services and business models based on the new sharing economy paradigm.

2

Energy can be traded among different entities in a community or among communities themselves, enabling new flexibility services.

3

This coordination requires digital technologies and new control algorithms. AI / ML and digital twin solutions can highly benefit from data availability.

Data Cellar – Groups of Use Cases per Beneficiary

Vision for technical and semantic interoperability

Where we start:

- Collect relevant input in terms of data collected by DATA CELLAR and other relevant Data Sets that could be relevant to DATA CELLAR:
 - Collected by DATACELLAR (Data Model)
 - Relevant to DATACELLAR (other initiatives)
- Compliance with IDSA/GAIA-X
- Mapping of components to the RAM of IDSA/GAIA-X
- Identify required components – not explicitly described in DOA (e.g. Federation services)

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Vision for technical and semantic interoperability

Traceability:

- Agreed identification taxonomy related to source of data

Surge ability:

- Agreed taxonomy facilitating intelligent grouping of data, that can be informative and exhaustive on specific attributes, services, applications etc
- Source related

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Vision for technical and semantic interoperability

- Deliver a data infrastructure platform for the (LEC-related) Data Cellar ecosystem based on distributed Energy Data Space (EDS) service offerings & resources in line with GAIA-X principles. **Open DEI** as the foundation upon which the Data Spaces Business Alliance will be further built.
- Support a range of standardized message exchange means (popular message brokers, APIs) to enhance technical federation potential with other data spaces, e.g., OpenAPI, AsyncAPI.

Data Cellar will reuse and/or develop comprehensive data model for energy community related use cases after analysis of existing semantic models, e.g. ontologies for energy data, such as the SAREF family and the Open Energy Ontology (OEO).
 Support the integration of such data model into general ontologies covering the entire scope of EDS.

15

GREEN AND DIGITAL TRANSITION

**Main impacts 1/2:
 Promote EU Energy System Green and Digital Transition**

- High quality data available and accessible through standardized and interoperable common European data spaces;
- Lead on the usage of data, data analysis models and energy efficient AI-based solutions for sustainable decision-making;
- Promote the use of Digital Twin and of AI applications by encouraging the development, sharing and use of algorithms for energy efficiency;

DATA CELLAR

**Main impacts 2/2:
Promote EU Energy System
Green and Digital Transition**

- Fully exploit the potential of technology such as **AI and Blockchain**, to support new and on-going energy communities to better manage their energy system;
- Take full advantage of digital technologies to **support smart and sustainable energy systems**.

27

DATA CELLAR

**Main impacts:
Promote Energy
Communities widespread
in Europe**

Enhance the creation and management of energy communities with the focus to:

- increase self-consumption thanks to the local renewable generation and providing flexibility services
- support in the optimal technology sizing
- support network operators to improve network operation and estimating network status and managing the distributed DSO resources.

DATA CELLAR

**Main impacts:
Promote Energy
Communities widespread
in Europe**

- Open new opportunities for profitable data-driven business models to support energy market players in speeding up their green transition, having a positive impact on the local economy.

The improved performance of the energy network will attract further investment and the development of industrial initiatives in the area.

DATA CELLAR

Thanks for listening

Questions?

Follow us:
Website <https://datacellarproject.eu>
LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/data-cellar-eu/>
Twitter https://twitter.com/DATACELLAR_EU

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8. Annex B

This annex includes material created for the module “Introduction to Energy Communities”.

Energy Communities – Introduction

- Energy transition: The role of the active users and the development/emergence of the Energy Communities

- Decentralized technology progress and engaged end users create conditions for efficient energy resource management.
- Active participation yields tangible benefits for all, driven by effective technology.
- Transitioning to new energy entities enhances resource utilization and aligns with an integrated grid approach.
- Optimal resource coordination becomes possible, maximizing efficiency and serving end users effectively.

EPL TECHNOLOGY FRONTIERS | DATA CELLAR

Energy Communities – General Definition

- Citizen groups, public authorities, organizations, and other entities directly involved in the energy market collaborate by jointly investing, generating, selling, and distributing renewable energy.
- The framework for Energy Communities was established in 2016 by the European Union (EU):
 - ✓ The right to participate in local services for production, distribution, aggregation, energy storage, and energy efficiency.
- A significant number of individuals and entities that would otherwise be unable to participate in the energy transition can now be involved.

4

EPL TECHNOLOGY FRONTIERS | DATA CELLAR

Energy Communities – Specific Definition

The Clean Energy Package formally recognizes specific community energy initiatives as "Energy Communities" within EU legislation.

- Energy Communities embody a collaborative approach to energy actions, emphasizing open participation and transparent governance.
- These communities not only promote sustainable energy practices but also offer tangible benefits to members and local communities.
- Energy Communities encompass a range of diverse energy models, showcasing innovative approaches to collective energy endeavors.
 - Across Europe, community energy projects take various forms, reflecting regional energy dynamics, needs, and resources.

3

Energy Communities – Official Definitions

- There are two official definitions of Energy Communities:
 - ✓ Citizens Energy Communities (CECs), as defined in the revised directive for the internal electricity market (EU) 2019/944.
 - ✓ Renewable Energy Communities (RECs), as defined in the revised directive for Renewable Energy Sources (EU) 2018/2001.
- These definitions delineate the scope and criteria for these distinct types of energy communities within the European regulatory framework.

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Energy Communities – Citizens Energy Communities (CECs)

- A “Citizens’ Energy Community” means a legal entity that:
 - ✓ Is based on voluntary and open participation and is under the substantial control of partners or members who are natural persons, local authorities including municipalities, or small businesses,
 - ✓ Has as its primary purpose to provide environmental, economic, and social benefits at the community level for its members or partners or for the local areas in which it operates, rather than to generate financial profits, and
 - ✓ Is capable of engaging in the production, including production from renewable sources, distribution, and supply of electricity, in consumption services, collective representation, energy storage, energy efficiency services, electric vehicle charging services, or providing other energy services to its partners or members.

7

Energy Communities – Renewable Energy Communities (RECs)

- A “Renewable Energy Community” means a legal entity that:
 - ✓ Relies on open and voluntary participation, operates autonomously, and is under the substantial control of shareholders or members who are closely connected to the renewable energy projects owned and developed by the said legal entity,
 - ✓ Whose shareholders or members are natural persons, small and medium-sized enterprises, or local authorities and municipalities,
 - ✓ Whose primary objective is to provide environmental, economic, and social benefits at the community level for its shareholders or members or for the local areas in which it operates, rather than financial profits.

8

- ### Energy Communities – Goals, Objectives and Benefits
- Environmental Resilience and Sustainability
 - ✓ Reducing Carbon Footprint: Promoting renewable energy sources
 - ✓ Mitigating Climate Impact: Lowering greenhouse gas emissions
 - ✓ Enhancing Biodiversity: Supporting eco-friendly energy practices
 - Economic Advancement
 - ✓ Local Energy Independence: Reducing reliance on external sources
 - ✓ Cost Savings: Lowering energy bills through shared generation and consumption
 - ✓ Job Creation: Fostering employment in renewable energy sectors
- EPL TECHNOLOGY FRONTIERS | DATA CELLAR

Energy Communities – Goals, Objectives and Benefits

- Social Benefits and Community Empowerment
 - ✓ Community Cohesion: Building stronger ties through shared energy initiatives
 - ✓ Energy Literacy: Educating members about energy conservation and renewables
 - ✓ Health and Well-being: Promoting cleaner air and a healthier environment
- Local Development and Resilience
 - ✓ Energy Security: Ensuring a stable energy supply during disruptions
 - ✓ Disaster Preparedness: Enabling energy self-sufficiency during emergencies
 - ✓ Strengthening Communities: Enhancing local infrastructure and resources

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Energy Communities – Goals, Objectives and Benefits

- Innovation and Technological Progress
 - ✓ Research and Development: Driving innovation in sustainable energy solutions
 - ✓ Technological Integration: Exploring smart grids, storage, and energy efficiency
 - ✓ Pilot Projects: Testing new energy technologies at a community level
- Democratic Governance and Participation
 - ✓ Inclusive Decision-Making: Empowering members to shape energy strategies
 - ✓ Transparent Management: Ensuring accountability and open communication
 - ✓ Community Influence: Prioritizing local interests in energy-related choices

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Energy Communities – Goals, Objectives and Benefits

- Education and Awareness
 - ✓ Knowledge Sharing: Educating members about the benefits of renewable energy
 - ✓ Outreach Programs: Spreading awareness about sustainable energy practices
 - ✓ Empowering Advocates: Enabling community members to become energy ambassadors
- Supporting National and EU Energy Objectives
 - ✓ Aligning with Renewable Targets: Contributing to national and EU renewable goals
 - ✓ Promoting Energy Efficiency: Encouraging energy-saving measures within the community
 - ✓ Policy Advocacy: Influencing policy decisions towards sustainable energy practices

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Energy Communities – Goals, Objectives and Benefits

- Long-Term Sustainability
 - ✓ Legacy for Future Generations: Creating a cleaner, more sustainable energy landscape
 - ✓ Transition Catalyst: Leading the way for broader adoption of renewable energy
 - ✓ Preserving Resources: Ensuring a balanced approach for energy consumption
- Enhancing Quality of Life
 - ✓ Creating Livable Spaces: Reducing pollution and environmental degradation
 - ✓ Promoting Prosperity: Economic growth and improved well-being through sustainable practices
 - ✓ Nurturing Communities: Building strong, resilient, and environmentally conscious neighborhoods

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Energy Communities - Energy Community Aspects

- **Activities**
 - ✓ Activities within energy communities encompass a wide range of functions, including energy production, supply, consumption, and distribution.
 - ✓ These communities also manage distribution networks for both electricity and heating.
 - ✓ Additionally, they engage in energy storage, provide energy services, and contribute to the advancement of electromobility.
 - ✓ Moreover, some energy communities offer financial services tailored to support community-based energy initiatives.
- **Energy Technologies**
 - ✓ Energy communities are powered by a diverse set of sustainable energy technologies.
 - ✓ These encompass wind power, solar power, small hydropower, bioenergy sources, heat pumps, district heating networks, and energy storage systems.
 - ✓ The integration of electric vehicles further contributes to the portfolio of energy technologies embraced by these communities.
- **Organizational Structure and Ownership**
 - ✓ Energy communities adopt various organizational models to manage their operations.
 - ✓ These include cooperative models, associations, corporate partnerships, and developmental commercial consortiums (known as TRAST).
 - ✓ Furthermore, private companies are also active participants in advancing the goals of community-driven energy initiatives.

Energy Communities - Energy Community Aspects

- **Geographical Spread and Size:**
 - ✓ Energy communities can be found at various geographical scales, ranging from the local to the regional and even national levels.
 - ✓ The size of these communities varies significantly, accommodating participation from a small number of members to larger groups comprising thousands of participants.
- **Diverse Participation Motivations**
 - ✓ Participation in energy communities is driven by a multitude of motivations. Various incentives encourage community members to get involved, fostering innovation in both societal and socioeconomic realms.
 - ✓ Examples of such motivations include the pursuit of energy self-sufficiency in villages, the establishment of co-housing communities, and the formation of agricultural cooperatives that collectively engage in sustainable energy practices.

Energy Communities - Who can participate?

- ✓ Individuals and entities such as citizen groups, public authorities, and organizations gain the right to engage directly in energy markets, collectively investing, generating, selling, and distributing renewable energy.
- ✓ Energy Communities enable a broad spectrum of stakeholders to participate actively in energy markets, fostering collaboration and sustainable practices.
- ✓ This inclusive approach extends participation to a diverse array of interested parties, ensuring a more comprehensive involvement in the energy transition.
- ✓ By facilitating joint efforts, a substantial number of individuals and entities, who might otherwise be excluded, can now contribute to and benefit from the energy transition.

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Energy Communities – Challenges

- Energy communities need to overcome:

TECHNICAL CHALLENGES

SOCIAL CHALLENGES

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Energy Communities – Challenges

As multifaceted cooperatives that fall under the social economy, they are called on to overcome a series of difficulties, mainly:

- Complexity of the institutional framework.
- The lack of appropriate expertise and information regarding insurance, accounting, and taxes both among market players and at the level of government services.
- The negative legacy left by the cooperative movement (in some countries).
- They must be active and viable in a highly competitive environment, the energy market, which in any case is in a phase of transformation.
- Need for a metering/communication infrastructure (in the case of CEC).

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Energy Communities - Energy Sources

Renewable Energy: An Overview

- Definition: Energy sources that are naturally replenished on a human timescale.
- Characteristics: Sustainable, Non-polluting, Reduced Carbon Footprint, Reduces reliance on fossil fuels.

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Energy Communities - Energy Sources

Solar and Wind Energy

- Solar Energy: Captures energy from the Sun using solar panels. Clean, abundant, and suitable for decentralized systems.
- Wind Energy: Converts kinetic energy from wind to electricity using turbines. Suitable for onshore and offshore setups.

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Energy Communities - Energy Sources

Hydroelectric and Geothermal Energy

- Hydroelectric Energy: Generates electricity by using water's gravitational force, often with dams. Sustainable but can impact local ecosystems.
- Geothermal Energy: Taps into Earth's internal heat for electricity generation. Consistent and reliable, especially in volcanic regions.

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Energy Communities - Energy Sources

Biomass Energy

- Definition: Organic material that comes from plants and animals, and can be used as a renewable energy source.
- Benefits: Carbon-neutral, reduces waste, supports agriculture.
- Drawbacks: Land use concerns, may compete with food sources.

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Energy Communities - Enabling Technologies

Storage & Flexibility in Local Resource Management

- Importance: Storing energy allows for balancing supply and demand, optimizing resource use.
- Types of Storage: Batteries (Lithium-ion, Flow batteries), Pumped hydro, Thermal storage.
- Flexibility: Ability to adapt to load changes, essential for integrating renewable sources which might be intermittent.

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Energy Communities - Enabling Technologies

Smart, Digitalised & Interoperable Integrated Grid

- Smart Grids: Electric networks that use digital technology to enhance grid operations, manage flow, and react to changes in usage.
- Digitalisation: Offers real-time data, improves efficiency, and enables predictive maintenance.
- Interoperability: Ensuring different parts of the grid can work seamlessly together, vital for integrating diverse energy sources and technologies.

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Energy Communities - Enabling Technologies

Data Management for Integrated Grids

- Significance: Efficient grid operation relies on precise data analytics, smart use of energy resources, utilizing the flexibility of demand in achieving more with less resources.
- Benefits: Predictive maintenance, real-time monitoring, improved customer experience.
- Challenges: Data privacy, cybersecurity, data integration from various sources.

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Energy Communities - Energy Conservation and Efficiency

The Role of Energy Conservation

- Definition: The practice of reducing energy use to save resources and reduce environmental impact.
- Importance: Helps in achieving sustainability, reduces strain on energy resources, combats climate change, and minimizes ecological footprint.

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Energy Communities - Energy Conservation and Efficiency

Energy Efficiency: A Pillar of Conservation

- Definition: Using less energy to perform the same task, optimizing energy output.
- Benefits: Reduced energy costs, increased resource longevity, and reduced emissions.

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Energy Communities - Energy Conservation and Efficiency

Everyday Energy Efficiency Tips

- Home: Use LED bulbs, seal windows and doors, install energy-efficient appliances.
- Transport: Opt for public transport, walk, bike, or use energy-efficient vehicles.
- Workplace: Turn off unused equipment, optimize heating and cooling, utilize natural light.

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Energy Communities - Energy Conservation and Efficiency

Strategies for a Greener Tomorrow

- Energy Audits: Identify where energy is wasted and how to rectify it.
- Sustainable Design: Incorporate energy efficiency in the design phase of buildings and products.
- Educate & Advocate: Increase awareness and promote energy conservation in communities.

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Energy Communities – Specific Examples

Examples/Pilot Projects of Energy Communities have been implemented in:

- Belgium
- United Kingdom
- Germany
- Spain
- Greece
- Denmark
- France
- Poland
- Sweden
- Netherlands

Vladimir Z. Gjorgjevski, Snezana Cundeva, George E. Georghlou, Social arrangements, technical designs and impacts of energy communities: A review, Renewable Energy

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Energy Communities – Examples - Belgium

BeauVent	
Name	BeauVent
Country	Belgium
Year	2000
Members	> 3 000
Organisation type	Cooperative Limited Liability Company (CVBA)
Activities	Generation renewable electricity, including the selling of electricity to those customers on whose roofs there are PV panels; Supply renewable heat; Energy efficiency; Third-party financing services
Technology / Energy	Wind, solar; Cogeneration; District heating network, biomass (waste incineration)
Renewable generation (or capacity)	Nieuwkapelle Park: 4 000 000 kWh; Gistel windmill: 2.4 MW; 993 976 kWh (2018)
Description	Beauvent is a cooperative that acts as a renewables producer. It sells the electricity it produces to Ecopower and large final customers. The cooperative also operates a district heating network. Beauvent collects funds to invest in wind energy, solar panels, biomass and energy-efficient applications such as CHP and heat networks.
Objectives	Target of 100% RES by 2050. Promotes using less energy and makes funds available for awareness raising and educational projects on energy issues. Encourage collective investment in renewables and low-energy houses. Ecological aims.
Website	https://www.beuvent.be

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - Belgium

Courant d’Air	
Name	Courant d’Air
Country	Belgium
Year	2009
Members	> 2000
Organisation type	Cooperative Limited Liability Company (SCRL)
Activities	Generation renewable electricity; Energy efficiency; Electro-mobility; Information awareness
Technology / Energy	Wind, solar; Collective LEDs, auditing and monitoring; car sharing
Renewable generation (or capacity)	-
Description	The cooperative pursues projects in the field of renewable energy and energy efficiency measures. It developed an education programme called Generation Zero Watt to incite future generations to be zero watt. Courant d’Air is open to everyone with a share subscription of €250.
Objectives	Aims at opening renewable energy access to as many people as possible. Promotes awareness and education. Improvements in energy efficiency.
Website	https://www.courantdair.be/wpf/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - Belgium

Ecopower

Name	Ecopower cvba
Country	Belgium
Year	1992
Members	56,000
Organisation type	Cooperative Limited Liability Company (CVBA)
Activities	Generation, supply renewable electricity; Supply renewable heat (biomass); Energy efficiency (Ecotrajat services)
Technology / Energy	Wind, solar, biomass, hydro, cogeneration; Wood eco-pellets, briquettes (domestic heating), micro-CHP
Renewable generation (or capacity)	~100 GWh/year electricity ; Towards 100% RES.
Description	Both an electricity producer and supplier of green electricity and renewable fuels in Flanders. It invests in wood pellets for small-scale heating of buildings and domestic hot water. Its Ecotrajat project assists citizens to commission deep energy renovations in their homes.
Objectives	Investments in 100% renewable energy. Supplies clean energy from local renewable sources to its members. Promotes energy efficiency.
Website	https://www.ecopower.be/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - United Kingdom

Edinburgh Community Solar Limited

Name	Edinburgh Community Solar Limited
Country	The United Kingdom
Year	2013
Members	541
Organisation type	Society for the Benefit of the Community (Solar Cooperative)
Activities	Generation, supply renewable electricity
Technology / Energy	Solar
Renewable generation (or capacity)	0 MW (public buildings, schools, community buildings and leisure centres); 1,107,250 kWh per year or 1.12 GWh/year
Description	Edinburgh Community Solar Cooperative (ECSC) has installed, owns and is now managing solar systems on the roofs of 24 City of Edinburgh Council buildings. This is the largest community-owned rooftop schema of this kind in the UK. During operation, some or all of the electricity generated is used by the building, depending on internal demand. This electricity is sold to the Council through a Licence Agreement, which is now in place. ECSC also receives income through the Feed in Tariff. Any surplus electricity is exported to the grid for which ECSC also receives an income.
Objectives	Open ownership of renewables for people of Edinburgh. Helps deliver low-carbon initiatives for buildings that host its panels. Helps other community groups that wish to tackle fuel poverty or reduce carbon emissions.
Website	https://www.edinburghsolar.coop/projects/how-the-co-op-works/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - United Kingdom

Isle of Eigg

Name	Isle of Eigg
Country	The United Kingdom
Year	2008
Members	96 local residents
Organisation type	Private limited Company Eigg Electric Ltd., a subsidiary of Community Heritage Trust
Activities	Generation, supply renewable energy (wind, hydro, solar); Distribution
Technology / Energy	Wind, hydro, solar; Independent grid management
Renewable generation (or capacity)	357 kW of electricity capacity; individual consumption limited to 5 kW/household
Description	The island, which was not connected to the UK's electricity grid, is the world's first community to launch an off-grid electric system powered by wind, water and solar.
Objectives	Cost-efficiency. Self-sufficiency (off-grid energy system to meet 24h electricity for a modern life). Sustainability (changing from diesel to electrification)
Website	http://isleofeigg.org/eigg-electric/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - Germany

Bioenergiedorf Jühnde eG

Name	Bioenergiedorf Jühnde eG
Country	Germany
Year	2005
Members	1089
Organisation type	Cooperative
Activities	Generation renewable electricity, generation and supply renewable heat; District heating networks (independent supply). The heat is distributed via a local grid to the households.
Technology / Energy	Wind, Solar, Biomass (silage, wood chips); Biogas, CHP; Village heating grid (gas)
Renewable generation (or capacity)	About 3 MWh of electricity is generated annually; heating grid supply of 4.3 MWh; About 3.5 MWh is used in the households annually.
Description	Jühnde is Germany's first village to produce heat and electricity by means of renewable biomass (plants in form of silage and wood chips), thus becoming the first village to be self-sufficient and produce RES with consumers participation.
Objectives	Meet the village's full energy demand by renewables. Sustainable energy use, avoiding fossil fuels, local solutions for solving climate change; Independent heat and electricity supply through biomass for agriculture, ecology and rural life
Website	http://www.bioenergiedorf.de/en/home.html

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - Germany

Elektrizitätswerke (EWS) Schönau eG	
Name	Elektrizitätswerke (EWS) Schönau eG
Country	Germany
Year	2005
Members	7300
Organization type	Cooperative Vertrieb GmbH
Activities	Renewation, supply, distribution (renewable electricity); supply and distribution of heat (district heating); bio and natural gas supply and distribution; Energy services; Electro-mobility; Others
Technology / Energy	Multi-energy: Wind, solar, biomass, biogas, CHP, heating networks; Tenant electricity models, services for electricity network operation, energy management; E-charging card
Renewable generation (or capacity)	-
Description	EWS Schönau is a multi-utility cooperative. In the late 1990s it was the first of its kind in Germany to take over the grid as well as electricity supply to the local community. When the electricity markets were deregulated in 1998, it started to sell almost exclusively renewable energy to its local electricity customers. The year after, EWS began to supply customers with green electricity on a nationwide scale. Its activities now also include the supply of natural gas and biogas.
Objectives	100% renewable energy goal. Campaigns against nuclear energy. Motivates people to instigate change. Civic engagement, co-determination and decentralisation.
Website	https://www.ews-schoenau.de/

(JRC, 2019)

Energy Communities – Examples - Germany

Elektrizitätswerke (EWS) Schönau eG	
Name	Elektrizitätswerke (EWS) Schönau eG
Country	Germany
Year	2005
Members	7300
Organization type	Cooperative Vertrieb GmbH
Activities	Renewation, supply, distribution (renewable electricity); supply and distribution of heat (district heating); bio and natural gas supply and distribution; Energy services; Electro-mobility; Others
Technology / Energy	Multi-energy: Wind, solar, biomass, biogas, CHP, heating networks; Tenant electricity models, services for electricity network operation, energy management; E-charging card
Renewable generation (or capacity)	-
Description	EWS Schönau is a multi-utility cooperative. In the late 1990s it was the first of its kind in Germany to take over the grid as well as electricity supply to the local community. When the electricity markets were deregulated in 1998, it started to sell almost exclusively renewable energy to its local electricity customers. The year after, EWS began to supply customers with green electricity on a nationwide scale. Its activities now also include the supply of natural gas and biogas.
Objectives	100% renewable energy goal. Campaigns against nuclear energy. Motivates people to instigate change. Civic engagement, co-determination and decentralisation.
Website	https://www.ews-schoenau.de/

(JRC, 2019)

Energy Communities – Examples - Spain

Som Energia

Name	Som Energia
Country	Spain
Year	2010
Members	59320
Organisation type	Cooperative
Activities	Generation, supply renewable electricity; Energy efficiency
Technology / Energy	Solar, Biogas, Wind, Hydro
Renewable generation (or capacity)	Annual generation of about 13.56 GWh.
Description	It is the first renewable energy cooperative in Spain. It was created with the aim of promoting sustainable development projects involving citizens' participation. Main activities include electricity commercialisation and renewables generation. It finances its own renewables projects through members' investments.
Objectives	Investments in green power plants. Towards 100% renewables. Provision of green electricity to its members at the generating cost of the power plant.
Website	https://www.somenergia.coop/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - Denmark

Marstal Fjernvarme

Name	Marstal Fjernvarme a.m.b.a.
Country	Denmark
Year	1962
Members	5600
Organisation type	Non-profit customer owned enterprise Marstal Fjernvarme A.m.b.a.
Activities	District heating network based on renewables (generation, distribution and supply) supplying about 2.200 customers on the island town of Marstal; Energy storage
Technology / Energy	Solar heat collectors (50-55%), wood chips (40%), heat pump (2-3%), Bio-oil, CHP; Thermal energy storage
Renewable generation (or capacity)	Annual production of about 32.000 MWh.
Description	Marstal Fjernvarme is an example of a solar district heating plant on the island of Årø, Denmark. The collectively-owned district heating network provides hot water to nearly all of the 2,200 inhabitants of the island town of Marstal. The company provides heat to Marstal from 100% renewables.
Objectives	The aim of the project is to demonstrate a large scale innovative, cost-effective and technically 100 % sustainable renewable energy system. It aims to demonstrate that district heating can be produced with 100% RES, of which solar thermal can cover 50% or more. This is done through a large heat storage combined with CHP using renewables to produce district heating. Green branding.
Website	https://www.solmarstal.dk/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - France

Mobicoop

Name	Mobicoop
Country	France
Year	2011
Members	20,000
Organisation type	Société coopérative d'intérêt collectif
Activities	Shared mobility
Technology / Energy	Car-pooling, car-sharing, public transport, shared bikes
Renewable generation (or capacity)	N/A
Description	Mobicoop is a cooperative in the field of shared mobility (car-pooling, car sharing). It ensures that shared mobility solutions are available to everyone (people with disabilities, the elderly, limited resources). The previous car-pooling association (Co-voiturage libre) has decided to turn into a cooperative (Mobicoop) in 2018.
Objectives	Promote electric car sharing services. Reduce transport emissions at the service of the greatest possible number. Tackle transport poverty (rural areas, disabilities)
Website	https://www.mobicoop.fr/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - France

Mobicoop

Name	Mobicoop
Country	France
Year	2011
Members	20,000
Organisation type	Société coopérative d'intérêt collectif
Activities	Shared mobility
Technology / Energy	Car-pooling, car-sharing, public transport, shared bikes
Renewable generation (or capacity)	N/A
Description	Mobicoop is a cooperative in the field of shared mobility (car-pooling, car sharing). It ensures that shared mobility solutions are available to everyone (people with disabilities, the elderly, limited resources). The previous car-pooling association (Co-voiturage libre) has decided to turn into a cooperative (Mobicoop) in 2018.
Objectives	Promote electric car sharing services. Reduce transport emissions at the service of the greatest possible number. Tackle transport poverty (rural areas, disabilities)
Website	https://www.mobicoop.fr/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - France

SAS Ségala Agriculture et Energie Solaire (SAS SAES)

Name	SAS Ségala Agriculture et Energie Solaire (SAS SAES)
Country	France
Year	2008
Members	180
Organisation type	Société Coopérative d'Intérêt Collectif Bois Énergie
Activities	Generation renewable electricity
Technology / Energy	Solar photovoltaics
Renewable generation (or capacity)	14 MW, 11 180 000 kWh; 461 agricultural buildings equipped with roofs.
Description	The Fermes de Figeac's solar PV project carried out by a specific firm SAS Ségala Agriculture et Energie Solaire. The initiative to install solar roofs on farm buildings was largely initiated as a reaction to the high feed-in-tariff in France.
Objectives	Mutualisation of a common resource as an additional income for the territory and cooperative. Guarantees regular income for farmers. Reinvest profits in local assets. Revitalisation of rural area where agricultural activities are on decline.
Website	https://www.farmesdefigeac.com/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - Poland

Zywiecka Energia Przyszłości

Name	Zywiecka Energia Przyszłości
Country	Poland
Year	2017
Members	40
Organisation type	Civic law cooperation agreement (energy cluster)
Activities	Generation renewable electricity, renewable heat source; Energy storage; Electro-mobility (retail only to members). Planned activities for energy supply and distribution.
Technology / Energy	Multiple (Bio CHP plant, Biogas reactor, Biomass boiler, Electric battery, EV charging station, Heat Pump, Solar heat collector, Solar PV system, Heat Storage, Hydro, distribution network)
Renewable generation (or capacity)	-
Description	The energy cluster was formed by signing a civic/legal contract between 20 public and private entities. It is a public-private network of cooperation whose main objectives are the production of electricity and balancing demand. It also includes distribution activities with a distribution network of less than 110 kV.
Objectives	Energy independence of Zywiec, reduce air pollution. Aims include: Distributing electricity, trading and balancing of energy demand; distribution of thermal energy; deploy local renewables in Zywiec region; electro-mobility; energy efficiency in public resources; reducing emissions in housing and public enterprises
Website	http://klasteryzywiec.pl/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - Sweden

Bostadsrättsföreningen Lyckansberg

Name	Bostadsrättsföreningen Lyckansberg
Country	Sweden
Year	2018
Members	33 tenanted-owned apartments
Organisation type	Housing association
Activities	Generation renewable electricity (solar plant); Consumption: Small-scale district heating
Technology / Energy	Solar, biomass
Renewable generation (or capacity)	Solar PV system size of 53 kW; yearly production of 55,000 kWh (PV)
Description	The housing association Lyckansberg's solar cell plant started to produce electricity in 2018. The plant generates electricity for common purposes, such as lighting, laundry cabins, sauna and other functions in the association hall. In case of surplus, PV electricity is sold online. If demand is higher, electricity is bought from the grid. The association also has district heating from Vaxjo Energi AB.
Objectives	Collective energy production. Collective ownership by the community.
Website	https://www.hsb.se/nydop/bf/lyckansberg/miljo/solcellar/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities – Examples - Netherlands

Duursma Ameland

Name	Duursma Ameland
Country	Netherlands
Year	2007
Members	9 partners (municipality of Ameland, Eneco, GasTerra, NAM, Signify, Lander, THO and Hanzel University of Applied Sciences Groningen / EnTerra, Ameland-Energie Coöperatie)
Organisation type	Public-Private Partnership (Consortium of companies together with municipalities)
Activities	Generation, supply renewable energy; Distribution (smart distribution network, devagation); energy efficiency (green lighting, school union light system); Public lighting; Electric-mobility (public transport (gas and electric buses))
Technology / Energy	Multiple: solar, smart energy grid, sustainable lighting, fuel cells, hybrid heat pumps, CHP, hydrogen, natural gas filling stations
Renewable generation (or capacity)	Solar park: installed capacity: 3,593.60 kWp; total production: 14,477,478.82 kWh
Description	Cooperation project between the municipality of Ameland, corporations, research institutes and the island's energy cooperative Ameland Energie Coöperatie. It is an example of cooperation with utilities and distribution system operator: Eneco, GasTerra, NAM, Signify, Lander, THO and Refractec. It is the first time that an innovative smart distribution network of this size has been developed in practice. The municipality is developing the largest smart electricity grid in the Netherlands. Duursma Ameland is the second largest solar park in the country. Ameland Solar Park is an initiative of the municipality of Ameland, Eneco and ABC.
Objectives	Permanently make the island's energy supply sustainable within a few years. With Duursma Ameland, the municipality of Ameland wants to achieve that the island can largely meet its own energy needs in 2030 in a sustainable way. The municipality is developing the largest smart electricity grid in the Netherlands.
Website	https://www.duursmaameland.nl/en/

(JRC, 2019)

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Energy Communities - Quiz

- Question 1:
 - ❖ What activities are commonly associated with energy communities?
 - a) Education and awareness campaigns
 - b) Only energy consumption
 - c) Energy production, distribution, storage, and services
 - d) Financial investments in large energy projects
- Question 2:
 - Which of the following technologies can be found in energy communities?
 - a) Traditional fossil fuel plants
 - b) Wind power, solar power, and bioenergy
 - c) Coal-fired power plants
 - d) Only nuclear reactors

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Energy Communities - Quiz

- Question 3:
 - ❖ What is the primary goal of energy communities?
 - a) Maximizing individual profits
 - b) Promoting energy waste
 - c) Providing environmental, economic, and social benefits to the community
 - d) Ignoring energy consumption patterns
- Question 4:
 - ❖ What is the organizational structure commonly found in energy communities?
 - a) Sole proprietorship
 - b) Government agency
 - c) Cooperative models, associations, corporate partnerships
 - d) International conglomerates

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Energy Communities - Quiz

- Question 5:
 - ❖ What role does active participation play in energy communities?
 - a) It is not encouraged as it complicates decision-making.
 - b) It leads to conflicts among members.
 - c) It fosters a sense of ownership and drives benefits for the community.
 - d) It has no impact on the community's energy initiatives.

- Question 6:
 - ❖ What are some examples of benefits that energy communities provide to their members?
 - a) Higher energy costs compared to traditional sources
 - b) Limited access to electricity and heating
 - c) Economic growth, reduced energy bills, and improved environmental quality
 - d) Only monetary dividends

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Energy Communities - Quiz

- Question 7:
 - ❖ How does an energy community support the energy transition?
 - a) By increasing reliance on fossil fuels
 - b) By ignoring technological advancements
 - c) By adopting sustainable energy technologies and practices
 - d) By focusing solely on economic growth

- Question 8:
 - ❖ What is the scale of participation in energy communities?
 - a) Participation is limited to a few large corporations.
 - b) Only individuals are allowed to participate.
 - c) Varies from local to regional to national levels, with varying membership sizes.
 - d) Participation is limited to government agencies.

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Energy Communities - Quiz

- Question 9:
 - ❖ What are some potential motivations for joining an energy community?
 - a) Environmental harm and energy waste
 - b) Maximizing personal profit at any cost
 - c) Societal innovation, energy self-sufficiency, and economic benefits
 - d) Isolation from the community
- Question 10:
 - ❖ Which of the following is NOT a benefit of energy communities?
 - a) Economic growth and job creation
 - b) Lower energy bills
 - c) Reduced carbon emissions and environmental impact
 - d) Limited access to modern energy services

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Energy Communities - Quiz

- Answers:
 1. c) Energy production, distribution, storage, and services
 2. b) Wind power, solar power, and bioenergy
 3. c) Providing environmental, economic, and social benefits to the community
 4. c) Cooperative models, associations, corporate partnerships
 5. c) It fosters a sense of ownership and drives benefits for the community.
 6. c) Economic growth, reduced energy bills, and improved environmental quality
 7. c) By adopting sustainable energy technologies and practices
 8. c) Varies from local to regional to national levels, with varying membership sizes.
 9. c) Societal innovation, energy self-sufficiency, and economic benefits
 10. d) Limited access to modern energy services

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Energy Communities - Recap - Key Points

- Energy Communities : Understanding of energy communities as groups collaboratively working towards sustainable energy goals.
- Enabling Technologies: Emphasizing storage, smart grids, and data management for efficient energy networks.
- Conservation & Efficiency: Highlighting the importance of reducing energy consumption and maximizing output.

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Energy Communities - Key Takeaways - The Significance Moving Forward

- Holistic Approach: Sustainable energy is not just about generation but also about efficient utilization and community collaboration.
- Future Preparedness: As energy demand grows, integrating renewable sources and managing them efficiently is paramount.
- Everyone's Role: Every individual, business, and community has a part to play in shaping a sustainable energy future.

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Thanks for listening

Questions?

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